



Figure 1. Interacting STE model representing interactions among feedback loops and enabling conditions of the six STEs identified for the food and land use system. The feedback loops are colour-coded to indicate their association with a particular STE: Education in green, Finance and land access in blue, Information feedbacks and lobbying in orange, Law and policy in red, Localisation and decentralisation in light blue and Norms and values in orange. Enabling conditions are shown as blue elements. Dashed arrows indicate that the respective enabling condition is a loop-external element and a solid arrow signifies that the enabling condition is a loop-internal element for the respective feedback loop that the element is connected to. Source: Own representation.